

TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION MANAGEMENT AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE AMONG 17 LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREAS IN ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT: This work studied the effect of technological innovation management on employee performance among 17 Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to; ascertain the effect of research and development analysis on increased productivity among 17 Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria and determine the effect of dynamic agent network on minimization of error among 17 Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study adopted a survey design. The population of the study was twelve thousand hundred eleven (12,011). The sample size of 387 was adopted using Taro Yamane statistical formula. The study used convenience sampling procedure and structured questionnaire was used to select respondents. Simple regression statistical tool was employed to test two formulated hypotheses. The findings revealed that research and development analysis have significant positive effect on increased productivity among 17 Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria (f-value = 8.258, and p value .000<0.05) and dynamic agent network has significant effect on minimization of error among 17 Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria (f-value = 7.158, and p value .000<0.05). Therefore, based on the findings, researcher also concluded that technological innovations have become an important part of organization administration as these technologies standardize office routines, relieve managers, enhances quality and accuracy of service delivery. The study thus recommends that management of local government should make available relevant modern office of research and development as a department in order to boost individual human capital development (skills acquisition and business entrepreneurs) across the grassroots.

INTRODUCTION

The creation of local government anywhere in the world stems from the need to facilitate development at the grassroots. The importance of local government is a function of its ability to generate a sense of belonging, safety and satisfaction among its populace. The Nigerian state therefore, created local government as the third tier of government whose objective is to ensure effective participation and promotion of government policies and programmes at the grassroots (Anikwe, Ogbuka & Nnamani, 2024).

Local government as a tier of government was first introduced in Nigeria in 1900 with the introduction of 1900 Native Ordinance. However, in 1976 efforts were made to reform and unify the local government system in Nigeria. The 1976 local government reform in Nigeria defined local government as the government at the local level exercised through representative councils, established by law to perform specific functions within a

defined area or through improvement of technological facilities/innovation (Anikwe, Ogbuka & Nnamani, 2024).

Technology innovation has huge impact on globalization, this enables Local Government of all sizes to do perfect administration with individual all over the world. In addition, Local Government can establish offices in practically any environment no matter how remote as long as there is Internet access. The competition for providing Internet access to developing nations proliferates, and enables growth in areas previously deprived of Government opportunities due to lack of communication devices (Nnamani & Nwoha, 2019).

A driving force for competitive scuffle in the present chaotic environment is technological innovation. Introducing new products and services are at the nucleus of economic growth and development (Okechukwu & Okoronkwo, 2018). In both developed and developing countries of the world, Local Governments have proofed to be prominent in terms of employment and added values to gross domestic product, 'yet their full potential remains untapped' (Zvirbule & Vilika, 2012). The support given for the start up of Local Governments, necessitate them to becoming important engines for innovation and technological advancement across various functions of Government (Okechukwu & Okoronkwo, 2018).

Productions of goods and services in the world today have been greatly influenced by the systematic application of physical forces through different types of technology innovation. Technology innovation in most organizations provides the required forces through various forms by which goods and services are produced. Technology innovation may be as a result of machine, equipment information and communication made up of knowledge, tools, method and system directed to work in specific manner (Nnamani & Nwoha, 2019).

Technology innovation is made up of the hardware innovation, the software innovation and the brain ware innovation though product innovation, market innovation, selling innovation etc. The hardware is the physical structure and logical of equipment, the software is knowledge and method used for - production or output from the hardware and the brain ware is the reason for using the technology in a particular way. All these depend on a particular way. sees technology to be the result of mans learned and acquired knowledge or his technical skills regarding how to do things well (Nnamani & Nwoha, 2019).

The state of technology innovation determines the quality and quantity of goods and services produced. Employee performance and development are determined by the types of technologies they use in production. Technology also influences living conditions of individual and groups in organizations and nations and the relationship between them. Technology is prone to innovation, creativity, and the state of technology have direct link to the relationship between the employer and employee (Nnamani & Nwoha, 2019). Hence, this study seeks to investigate the effect of technological innovation management on employee performance among 17 Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The state of technology in any local governments influences the quality and quantity of administration. But despite this, technology is prone to constant innovation in local government have to monitor, manage and cope with. Local governments that want to be competitive and profitable should ensure that employees are trained and involved in the management of technological innovation for survival and positive output. But most local

governments tend to undermine the contribution of employees in managing technological innovation, the outcome of which are low output and performance. The problem is that management cum employees may not be abreast and informed on the innovative changes in the ever-dynamic technological innovation and they may have not strategy to effectively tackle this trend for increase in output and employment generation to our teeming individuals.

It has been observed that the main cause of poverty in underdeveloped local governments is that they suffer from the technological backwardness. A specific level of technological advancement is the necessary pre-condition for rapid growth. Therefore, the task of technological innovation in underdeveloped local governments is difficult because the social set up in backward pre-industrial economies is not conducive to technological improvements on any significant scale. The absence of proper technological innovation retards the economic growth, reduces rate of administrative outputs and equally encourages unemployment. Thus, it is imperative either to explore new technology or import technology from industrially advanced countries to promote the economic growth of 17 Local Government Areas of Enugu State.

Innovations in technology have the potential to decrease the time needed to complete a task, or in some cases eliminate the need for a business process or job function. Typically, the desire for increased productivity drives upgrades to technology within Local Government Areas, which can significantly influence its operations and achievement. Repeated economic crises and steadily increasing competition, brought about in particular by the globalization of markets, are forcing an unprecedented rationalization of resources. These and other short comings gave rise for this study and it is designed to proffer solution for our Local Government Areas to remain in the protection and security of individuals not minding the recession that has crippled all facet of our economy.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the effect of technological innovation management on employee performance among 17 Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria. Specific objectives were to;

- i. Ascertain the effect of research and development analysis on increased productivity among 17 Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria.
- ii. Determine the effect of dynamic agent network on minimization of error among 17 Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Technological

Technology is a systematic application of physical forces for production of goods and services. The knowledge used in practical ways in industry (Oxford 2005). It is the knowledge, process, tools, methods and systems employed in the creation of goods and improving in services. Technology is the result of man's learned and acquired knowledge or his technical skills regarding how to do things well (Khalil, 2020).

Innovation

Innovation can be defined as the application of new ideas to the products, processes, or other aspects of the activities of a firm that lead to increased "value." This "value" is defined in a broad way to include higher value added for the firm and also benefits to consumers or other firms.

Management

Management is a process of planning, decision making, organizing, leading, motivation and controlling the human resources, financial, physical, and information resources of an organization to reach its goals efficiently and effectively (Dill, 2021).

Innovation Management

Mekhala Roy (2019) defined that Innovation management involves the process of managing an organization's innovation procedure, starting at the initial stage of ideation, to its final stage of successful implementation.

Technological Innovation Management

Technological innovation provides the life-blood of economic activities. Technological innovation is a tool for economic growth and the application of those inventions to meet emerging business opportunities, and to meet social needs, and environmental challenges. For any organization to be able to compete, it must be technologically innovative. Technological innovation and core competitiveness enjoy symbiotic relationship (Prhanlad & Hamel, 2019).

Research and Development Analysis

R&D is a significant driver of innovation, leading to the development of new products, services and process. These innovations can spur economic growth by creating new markets and improving productivity; increasing competitive advantage in a global market; creating skilled jobs across the world and having spillover effects across sectors (Prhanlad & Hamel, 2019).

Dynamic Agent Network

The goal of using an agent simulation for generating the network is to use a realistic bottom up approach. Such models focus on agent behaviors, based on some extend on real human action. Moreover, these methods facilitate the use of real-world data as input and validation (Parunak, *et al.* 2019).

Employee Performance

Nmadu (2023) employee performance is a degree of accomplishment of task(s) that make up an employee's job. This process requires knowledge of what activities and outputs are designed, observing whether they occur and providing feedback to help improve employee morale and to meet expectation (Nmadu, 2023). However, employee performance is associated with productivity which translates to quantity of output, quality of output, timeliness of output, presence or attendance on the job, morale at work, efficiency of the work completed and effectiveness of work completed (Mathis, Fredrick & Kenneth, 2019).

Increased Productivity

Productivity is an attitude of mind, it is a mentality of progress, the consistent improvement in a work place. It is the certainty of being able to do better today than yesterday and continuously in realization of goals (Anikwe, Ogbuka & Nnamani, 2024).

Minimization of Error

In organizational behavior the norms or expectations for behavior or its consequences can be derived from the intention of the actor or from the expectations of other individuals. Errors are a recurring fact of organizational life and can potentially yield either adverse or positive consequences. Every organization is confronted with errors. Errors can result in negative consequences as well as positive ones. One way to contain the negative and

to promote the positive consequences of errors is to use error management. The error management approach distinguishes between errors and their consequences. Error management culture implies that a firm accepts that people make errors and uses “organizational practices related to communicating about errors, to sharing error knowledge, to helping in error situations, and to quickly detecting and handling errors” to deal with errors (Fischer, Frese, Mertins & Hardt-Gawron, 2018).

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework used in this study is Wolfensohn's (Wolfensohn, 2000). He claims that technical innovation refers to the finding of new and better ways to manufacture commodities. Changes in technology result in higher labour, capital, and other productivity. It can be utilised to boost value in a variety of areas, including financial, social, physical, and intellectual. He divided the technological stages in the office information and management field into four separate stages, which he believes advanced countries go through before reaching the stage of development. The stages are research and development, ascent, maturity, and decline, according to Wolfensohn 2000. Innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards are the five chronological demographics that make up the adoption of various technologies. To do so, you must first identify an issue, then produce various solutions, choose the best one, build a model, test it, tweak and retest it as needed, then present the final solution. As a result, the framework's assumption is based on the above-mentioned steps, which must be implemented to suit the needs of information managers and management in general.

Empirical Review

Research and Development Analysis and Increased Productivity

Ukwuoma, Amade and Moghalu (2013) investigated the management of research and development (r&d) for commercialization in Nigeria. This study aimed at investigating some of the factors that could affect the management of R&D results for commercialization. The result of Multiple Regression of R&D Management Structure (Y) on the three independent variables (X1, X2 and X3) affecting the management of R&D results for commercialization showed a significant R value of 0.973 and Coefficient of determination of 0.962. The study also identified that a significant relationship exists among implicit factors, explicit factors, technology brokering influences and R&D management structure.

Dynamic Agent Network and Minimization of Error

Audren, Frederic and Benoit (2020) studied dynamic agent-based network generation in Malaysia. The idea is to use an agent-based simulation to generate networks: agent behaviors are rules for the network construction. Resulting generated networks are compared to a target network; the system automatically looks at the best behavior distribution to generate this specific target network.

Muhammad and Nadeem (2014) conducted a study on the impact of technological advancement on employee performance in Nigeria banking sector. The purpose of this study was to check the impact of technological advancement on employee performance in banking sector. The findings indicate that technological advancement has significant impact on motivation and training of employees. Motivation has significant impact on employee performance but training has no significant impact on employee performance.

Adeyeyetolulope (2014) examined the impact of technological innovation on organizational performance in Nigeria. This study investigated the impact of technological innovation on organizational performance. The findings from the study revealed that strategic planning and marketing capability independently and jointly influence organizational performance. Also, there is positive interaction between performance variables (i.e resources availability, staff quality, productivity, sales revenue, financial strength, public image and good will).

Okechukwu and Okoronkwo (2018) carried out a study on evaluation of technological environment on organizational performance among selected medium scale enterprise in Enugu State. The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of technological environment on organizational performance. Descriptive research design was adopted in the study among 217 staff of the selected medium scale enterprises in Enugu. The result of the study shows that technological environment has no significant role on organizational customer satisfaction among selected Small and medium scale enterprises in Enugu and technological environment has a significant effect on organizational market share among selected Small and medium scale enterprises in Enugu.

In Kogi State, Enijini (2018) investigated the impact of technological innovation on the performance of information managers in government Parastatals. The research is based on the science and technology studies (STS) tradition, which investigates how social interactions and institutions drive innovation in science and technology, as well as the technological qualities that affect social arrangements when implemented. The findings suggest that there is a social interaction between technology innovation and office information managers and management that can shape office information and management.

Gabriel (2020) explored the impact of technological innovation on office workers in private organisations in Edo State, collecting and analysing relevant secondary data to reach the paper's goal. The outcome demonstrates that technological innovation aids in the transformation of the office system in order to meet organisational objectives.

Hammed and Ronke (2024) examined roles of technological innovation in enhancing the service delivery of information managers in public organizations in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The broad aim of this study was to examine the roles of technological innovation in enhancing service delivery of information managers in public organizations in Ekiti State. The researcher used a survey Findings revealed that the use of technological innovations such as computers and other ICT facilities have and play a significant role on the service delivery of information managers.

Nnamani and Nwoha (2019) examined trend in technological changes and its effect on organizational performance of manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. A survey research design was adopted. The study revealed that trend in rapid technological changes have positively and significantly contributed to the profit of manufacturing firms in Enugu State based on t-calculated $65.29 > \text{critical value } t(1.645)$. Also trend in rapid technological changes have positive and significance effect on employment generation of manufacturing firms in Enugu State. This was also based on t-calculated $(71.58) > \text{critical value } t(1.645)$.

Anikwe, Ogbuka and Nnamani (2023) examined enhancing staff recruitment efficiency and operational performance within Nigeria's Local Government Framework. This study examined staff recruitment and productivity in local government system in Enugu State 1999-2021. The researcher adopted descriptive survey design. Multi stage sampling techniques were adopted for the study. A self-structured questionnaire was used to collect data. The findings indicated that there is a relationship between staff recruitment and low productivity in local government system in Enugu State.

Gap in Empirical Review

The study reviewed technological innovation management and employee performance. The study reviewed related literatures which were of great importance in establishing knowledge in the present. Nevertheless, there exist gaps in the reviews as the studies were indirectly related to the present study this was because the objective of the present study was on research and development, dynamic agent network where as that of the reviewed studies were on increased productivity and minimization of error. Gap also exist in the area of the study as the present study was conducted in a different location from the reviewed studies. This study tends to be the most recent study from the reviewed works and as such would be found worthy to fill in this gap.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed the survey research design. According to George (2017), survey is the investigation of behaviour, opinion or other manifestation of a group of people by questioning them. Furthermore, primary data and secondary was adopted, using both qualitative and quantitative analytical tools to examine the effect of technological innovation management on employee performance. The data used in this research were sourced from the questionnaire and text book, internet source etc.

Population for the Study

Table 1: The population for the study consisted staff of 17 local government areas of Enugu State. The populations used for this study were illustrated in table below;

S/No	Local Governments	Address	Population
1	Nsukka	Nsukka Town	1,025
2	Uzo-uwani	Uzo-uwani	1,001
3	Igbo-Etiti	Igbo-Etiti	1, 010
4	Aninri	Aninri	600
5	Awgu	Awgu	520
6	Enugu East	Enugu East	815
7	Enugu North	Enugu North	706
8	Enugu South	Enugu South	620
9	Ezeagu	Ezeagu	600
10	Igbo-Eze North	Igbo-Eze North	604
11	Igbo-Eze South	Igbo-Eze South	520
12	Isi-Uzo	Isi-Uzo	505
13	Nkanu East	Nkanu East	620
14	Nkanu West	Nkanu West	715
15	Orji River	Orji River	700
16	Udenu	Udenu	710
17	Udi	Udi	740
	Total		12,011.

Source: The Head of Service Enugu State Secretariat, 2025

Sample size of the study was calculated using Taro Yamane (1967) statistical formula which is used in determining the sample size of a known population as shown below: -

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n = The required sample size.

n = Population of study = 12,011

e = Level of significant 5% = 0.05

1 = constant

$$n = \frac{12,011}{1 + 12,011 (0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{12,011}{31.02}$$

n = 387 Sample Size

Thus, the research instrument used to carry out this study was structured questionnaire method. Extensive use was made of the questionnaire as a basic tool. More so, multiple choice questions were used in designing the questionnaire in an attempt to exhaust all the possible responses which is relevant to the work. The questionnaire was made up of 5 points Likert scale strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree (SA-SD). For each variable, there were (items/elements) which were deployed keeping in view the questionnaire filling culture and understanding of the population. Data for the study were analyzed using frequency distribution table, and percentages to analyze the data from the questionnaire, while simple regression was used to analyze the hypotheses.

Test of Hypotheses

The hypotheses were tested using simple regression method. The following steps were taken:

- i) The hypotheses were restated in null and alternate forms.
- ii) The regression results were presented and analyzed, and
- iii) The decision involving the rejection or acceptance of the null hypothesis based on the decision criterion of the techniques of analysis is made.
- iv) Statement of decision rule (accept if p-value is less than 0.5%, or reject if p-value is high than 0.05%), while coefficient measures direction whether it has positive or negative sign.

Test of Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Research and development analysis does not have significant positive effect on increased productivity among 17 Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria.

H₀₁: Research and development analysis have significant positive effect on increased productivity among 17 Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Table 4.2: ANOVA of the Regression Model

Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sign
Regression	33.451	3	5.409	8.258	0.000
Residual	213.687	247	.655		
Total	216.138	350			

Source: Extracted from SPSS Version 25

Table 4.3: Estimated Regression of the Model

Model	Coefficient	Std. error	t	Sign
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Constant	0.007	0.241	4.4173	0.000
Research and development analysis	0.067	0.031	2.169	0.000

Fitness Model of the Variables

In statistics, the relation value between the independent and dependent variables is indicated using the significance testing hence a significance number less than 0.05 which is the probability value shows a model significant in explaining the variables relations.

An analysis of variance was calculated and the results showed a statistically significant model which is translated as the independent variables supports the dependent variable (Research and development analysis). The F statistic was also in support with a value of 8.258 and a critical value of (0.000) which is less the 0.05 significance level.

Results of the regression of coefficients in table 4.3 show a significant effect between research and development analysis and on increased productivity among 17 Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria, since the beta coefficients obtained 0.067 respectively. This shows that a unit change in the independent variables would result to a change in the dependent variable. The result shows that research and development analysis has significant positive effect on increased productivity among 17 Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Dynamic agent network does not have significant positive effect on minimization of error among 17 Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: Dynamic agent network have significant positive effect on minimization of error among 17 Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Table 4.4: ANOVA of the Regression Model

Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sign
Regression	33.351	3	6.409	7.158	0.000
Residual	244.787	247	.755		
Total	283.238	350			

Source: Extracted from SPSS Version 25

Table 4.5: Estimated Regression of the Model

Model	Coefficient	Std. error	t	Sign
Constant	0.147	0.341	3.4173	0.000
Dynamic agent network	0.167	0.231	3.169	0.000

Fitness Model of the Variables

In statistics, the relation value between the independent and dependent variables is indicated using the significance testing hence a significance number less than 0.05 which is the probability value shows a model significant in explaining the variables relations.

An analysis of variance was calculated and the results showed a statistically significant model which is translated as the independent variables supports the dependent variable (dynamic agent network) in Enugu metropolis. The F statistic was also in support with a value of 7.158 and a critical value of (0.000) which is less than the 0.05 significance level.

Results of the regression of coefficients in table 4.5 show a significant effect between dynamic agent network and minimization of error among, since the beta coefficients obtained 0.167 respectively. This shows that a unit change in the independent variables would result to a change in the dependent variable. The result shows that dynamic agent network has significant effect on minimization of error among 17 Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis One: Results of hypothesis one shows the relation value between the independent and dependent variables is indicated using the significance testing hence a significance number less than 0.05 which is the probability value shows a model significant in explaining the variables relations. This is in agreement with study of Ukwuoma, Amade and Moghalu (2013) investigated the management of research and development (r&d) for commercialization in Nigeria. The result of Multiple Regression of R&D Management Structure (Y) on the three independent variables (X1, X2 and X3) affecting the management of R&D results for commercialization showed a significant R value of 0.973 and Coefficient of determination of 0.962.

Hypothesis Two: Results of hypothesis two shows the relation value between the independent and dependent variables is indicated using the significance testing hence a significance number less than 0.05 which is the probability value shows a model significant in explaining the variables relations. This is consistent with study of Audren, Frederic and Benoit (2020) studied dynamic agent-based network generation in Malaysia. The idea is to use an agent-based simulation to generate networks: agent behaviors are rules for the network construction. Resulting generated networks are compared to a target network; the system automatically looks at the best behavior distribution to generate this specific target network.

Summary of Findings

- i. Research and development analysis has significant positive effect on increased productivity among 17 Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria (f-value = 8.258, and p value .000<0.05).
- ii. Dynamic agent network has significant effect on minimization of error among 17 Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria (f-value = 7.158, and p value .000<0.05).

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concludes that technological innovations have become an important part of organization administration as these technologies standardize office routines, relieve managers, enhances quality and accuracy of service delivery. The study stressed that with the advancement in technology, the performances of information managers in public organizations are better enhanced. The study also concludes that technological innovation management had significant positive effect on employee performance among 17 Local Government Areas in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made as follows:

- i. The management of local government should make available relevant modern office of research and development as a department in order to boost individual human capital development (skills acquisition and business entrepreneurs) across the grassroots.
- ii. The management of local government should give the human personnel management managers opportunities to establish training on dynamic agent network among staff to enable them operate with modern trend of technological innovation across global.

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